

ROLE OF INTELLECTUAL SYSTEMS IN THE TRAINING OF RESERVE AND RESERVE OFFICERS IN THE MILITARY EDUCATION UNITS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: In the article the main directions and proposals for the use of intellectual education systems in the training of reserve and reserve officers in the military training system are presented.

Key words: intelligent training systems, officer in reserve and reserve, distance learning support technologies, competence-based approach.

Intelligent system (IS) educational systems is a qualitatively new technology, the characteristics of which are the modeling of the educational process using a dynamically developing knowledge base; automatic selection of a reasonable teaching strategy for each student, automatic recording of new information entering the database.

Intellectualization of modern information-educational resources is currently one of the most promising directions of joint research with teachers, psychologists and experts in the field of information-educational technologies.

In order to adequately maintain the country's defense capabilities and security, the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan should have qualitatively prepared, as well as structurally and quantitatively balanced reserve officers. Their training is part of the general system of military-professional training, during which the psychological readiness of reserve and reserve officers for military service is formed and developed. The specific characteristics of the process of training a military specialist and the military educational environment of an educational institution are determined by the characteristics of military professional activity.

It is aimed at achieving the necessary level of professional competence of military specialists and ensuring their professional training at a high level in the system of professional education.

Today, the military-professional education system still needs research to find pedagogical tools and methods that allow training of high-quality reserve and reservist officers. The use of artificial intelligence methods and tools in the field of automated training of intelligent training systems (ITT), which is rapidly developing today, to the training system of military specialists in higher educational institutions

It is inevitable that intelligent learning systems, one of the new trends in the training of mature professionals, will become the main technologies of the future. Intelligent

learning systems (ITT) are a practical result of the use of artificial intelligence methods and tools in the field of automated learning and represent a new generation of learning systems. In order to achieve the maximum possible result in the field of the student's potential development during the educational process, the subject teacher uses three main types of special knowledge: knowledge about the subject of teaching, knowledge about teaching methods, and knowledge about the student. In traditional automated learning systems, parts of this information are strictly included in the text of individual frames of the training course according to the chosen teaching methodology. Artificial in ITT of intellect different methods and from technologies used without necessary knowledge separate shown . From this knowledge used without ITT of the student psychophysiological and intellectual capabilities looking the most efficient teaching methods training material present reach speed and methods choose his content size and complexity through regulation sh study process by individualizing his quality increase . intellectual technologies reveal new ways of improving the quality of educational services in the modern information society.

There are two types of technology for building a sequence of a training course: active and passive. An active sequence implies the existence of a learning goal (a small part of the concepts of the studied subject area that must be mastered). Most of the existing systems have a strict educational goal - a complete set of curriculum concepts. Many flexible goal systems allow the teacher or student to select subsets of learning goal concepts as current goals.

Passive (corrective) sequencing is a feedback technique that does not require an active learning goal. This is triggered if the user cannot solve the problem or answer the question correctly. Correction technology in this case offers the user a part of the existing information material that can fill the gap in the student's knowledge to solve the error.

A rational analysis of student decisions is related to the student's final answers to educational tasks (it does not matter how these answers were obtained). The purpose of the intelligent decision analyzer is to determine whether the solution proposed by the student is correct or incorrect, to find out what exactly is wrong or incomplete in the answer, and to provide him with additional information to fill the gap in the student, who may have missing or incorrect knowledge. Intelligent analyzers can provide remote feedback to learners and update the learner's model.

Interactive help in completing tasks - this technology provides intellectual support to the student at each stage of completing tasks, instead of waiting for the final solution. The level of support can be different: from warning about a wrong step, giving advice and setting the next step for the student. Systems implementing this technology (often referred to as interactive simulators) can monitor the learner's actions, use them to assist with comprehension and understanding, and update the learner's model.

Supportive technology is the oldest as examples in performing tasks. This technology helps students to solve new problems, not to emphasize their mistakes, but to give examples of similar problems that have been successfully solved before. It can be seen that intellectual technologies reveal new ways to improve the quality of educational services in the modern information society. Intelligent electronic means of monitoring and teaching allow to adapt to a specific student and organize the educational process in accordance with his level of knowledge. The use of intelligent electronic tools allows increasing the efficiency of independent learning of students and reducing time, which is very important for open and distance education.

References:

1. Umarov, I. O. (2021). HARBIY TAYYORGARLIK O 'QUV MARKAZIDA REZERVDAI VA ZAXIRADAGI OFITSERLARNI TAYYORLASH: AN'ANALARI, INNOVATSIYALARI, ISTIQBOLLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(9), 939 -944.
2. Olimjonovich, U. I. (2022). AMIR TEMURNING 1391 YILDA OLTIN O'RDAGA QILGAN HARBIY YURISHI. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 1(11), 368-371.
3. Olimjonovich, U. I. (2022). IKKINCHI JAHON URISHIDA O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT QURILISHI MAYDONCHASIGA AYLANISHI. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 2(23), 193-197.
4. Olimjonovich, U. I., Mirhokimovich, T. A., & Ibragimovich, A. I. (2022). ARMED FORCES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(4), 1884-1892.
5. Olimjonovich, U. I., Mirhokimovich, T. A., & Ibragimovich, A. I. (2022). QOMUSIMIZ-ERKIN VA FAROVON HAYOTIMIZ KAFOLATI. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 2(24), 244-253.
6. Olimjonovich, U. I., Rahmatali o'g'li, E. S., Nurali o'g, J. R. S., Ikromjon o'g'li, I. S., & Ahrorjon o'g'li, K. A. (2022). HARBIY BILIM YURTLARIDA HARBIY PSIXOLOGIYA FANINING O'RGATISH AFZALLIKLARI VA AHAMIYATI. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(4), 415-419
7. Turdiboyev, S., & Abdurakhimov, I. (2021). COPYRIGHT IS THE FOUNDATION OF OUR DEVELOPMENT. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 1159-1160.
8. Kamoliddinovich, N. M. (2022). The Role of Military Pedagogy and Psychology in the Armed Forces. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 372-373.
9. Ogli, Y. A. B., Ogli, A. I. N., & Abdulaev, A. (2021). The Main Directions of Military Patriotic Education. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 1(1), 99-100.
10. Юнусов, М. М., Сабирова, Г. Х., & Абдурахимов, И. Н. У. (2022). ИНФЕКЦИОННЫЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ И ИХ ПРОФИЛАКТИКА. *Science and innovation*, 1(D3), 87-88.
11. Salijanovna, I. S., Sherbabayevna, H. Q., Rahmanova, M. Y., Nabibullayevich, X. F., & O'G'Li, A. I. N. (2022). O'SIB KELAYOTGAN YOSH AVLODGA TA'LIMIY VA DIDAKTIK O'YINLAR ORQALI TA'LIM BERISHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B3), 18-22.

12. Toxir, T., Arabboy, Y., Zuxriddin, G., & Abdurauf, G. (2022). Theoretical And Practical Pedagogical Bases of Formation of Professional Culture of Students of Military Education. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2, 19-20.
13. Toxir, T., Arabboy, Y., Zuxriddin, G., & Abdurauf, G. (2022). Theoretical And Practical Pedagogical Bases of Formation of Professional Culture of Students of Military Education. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2, 19-20.
14. Abdugafurovich, T. T. (2022). ЁШЛАРДА СОҒЛОМ МАФКУРА ВА ВАТАНПАРВАРЛИК ТУЙҒУСИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. О'ЗБЕКISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 1(8), 846-849.
15. Abdugafurovich, T. T. (2021). The Importance of Forbidden Islam in Spiritual Growth, Problems and Solutions. *International Journal of Human Computing Studies*, 3(1), 141-143.
16. Абдугафурович, Т. Т. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКISTON ЁШЛАРИДА ВАТАНПАРВАРЛИК ТУЙҒУСИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 2(22), 444-446.
17. Abdugafurovich, T. T. (2021). In The Process of Educating Students of the Faculty of Military Education in the Spirit of Patriotism the Invaluable Contribution and Significance of the Uzbek People to the Victory Over Fascism (Dedicated to the 76th anniversary of The Victory of the Seco. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 2(4), 90-93.
18. Abdugafurovich, T. T. (2021). The importance of pedagogical ideas in the formation of youth. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 1066-1069.
19. Тургунбаев, Т. А. (2021). Вклад и значение узбекского народа в победу над фашизмом (к 76-летию Победы во Второй мировой войне). *Молодой ученый*, (18), 485-488.
20. Тургунбаев, Т. А., & Каримов, Ў. У. (2020). ҲАММА НАРСА-ФРОНТ УЧУН, ҲАММА НАРСА-ҒАЛАБА УЧУН!(ИККИНЧИ ЖАҲОН УРУШИДА ҚОЗОНИЛГАН ҒАЛАБАНИНГ 75 ЙИЛЛИГИГА БАҒИШЛАНАДИ). *Интернаука*, (19-4), 52-53.
21. Abdugafurovich, T. T., & Shokhmukhammad, M. (2021). THE ROLE OF EDUCATING STUDENTS IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(9), 126-130.
22. Tahirjon, T. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF SPIRITUALITY AND PATRIOTISM IN THE MIND OF STUDENTS. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(10), 299-304.
23. Tojimatovich, A. A., Musajanovich, K. M., & Khoshimovich, A. B. (2022). On Approval of the Concept of Education of Youth in the Spirit of Military and Patriotism. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 13, 6-8.
24. Tojimatovich, A. A., Musajanovich, K. M., & Khoshimovich, A. B. (2022). On Approval of the Concept of Education of Youth in the Spirit of Military and Patriotism. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 13, 6-8.
25. Охунова, Д. К., & Шоюсупова, О. А. (2016). PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF HARMONIOUS EDUCATION OF STUDENTS. *Учёный XXI века*, (5-1 (18)), 42-45.
26. Oxunova, D. (2022). О 'QUVCHILAR BILIMINI BAHOLASHGA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(2), 870-876.

27. Охунова, Д. К., & Шоюсупова, О. А. (2016). ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ГАРМОНИЧНОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ. Ученый XXI века, (5-1), 45.
28. Kahhorjonovna, O. D. (2022). Approaches to Preparing Future Teachers for the Organization of Cognitive Processes in General Secondary Schools. Miasto Przyszłości, 29, 6-7.
29. Kahhorjonovna, O. D. (2022). Future Teachers' Specific Characteristics of Development of Cognitive Acceptance of Professional Knowledge. Miasto Przyszłości, 29, 1-2.
30. Okhunova, D. K. (2022, October). APPROACHES TO EXPANDING THE POSSIBILITIES OF COGNITIVE ACCEPTANCE OF PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE TEACHERS. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 26-32).
31. SUMMATIV, O. Q. B. F. V., & MEXANIZMLARI, B. DQ Oxunova–Farg’ona davlat universiteti o ‘qituvchi. FARG ‘ONA DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI, 423.